

Mortality in times of COVID. Are democracies better at controlling the outbreak?

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Abstract

The COVID pandemic hit countries around the globe differently. Besides the biological and demographic factors, the social norms and institutions frame the impact of the health emergency, by instilling values and norms helping people to adapt their behavior. Democracy seems to be better prepared for facing the health emergency, because of its good health outcomes and the ability to cope with disasters, democratic governed societies are vulnerable in the face of COVID because of the longer life expectancy of their public which plays against democracy, as the empirical evidence shows the disease hit mainly old adults. This paper inquires whether democratic societies still have an advantage in dealing with the COVID crisis, proving with empirical data that COVID mortality is lower in highly advanced democracies.

Keywords

Political rule; COVID pandemic; mortality

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Introduction

SARS-COV2 was declared a pandemic in March 2020, affecting countries all over the world. Although the fight against the virus was coordinated by the World Health Organization (WHO), the pandemic hit differently, with the infection rate and the death toll varying from one society to another. Besides the biological and demographic factors, the social norms and institutions frame the impact of the health emergency, by instilling values and norms helping people to adapt their behavior.

While most of the COVID pandemic literature focuses on biological and demographic factors, this paper looks at how political rule may influence the severity of the pandemic by fostering social values with an impact on individual behavior related to containment measures. At first glance, democracy seems to be better equipped to face health emergencies, as compared to autocracy, due to better health outcomes (Patterson and Veenstra, 2016; Bollyky et al, 2019) and the ability to cope with disaster-related emergencies (Strömberg, 2007). However, democracy fosters the growth of individual well-being (Inglehart 2018) leading to the growth of life expectancy (Mackebach et al, 2013; Bollyky et al, 2019) and this plays against democracy, as the empirical evidence shows that the impact of COVID is higher among old adults (Beam Dowd et al, 2020). Therefore, is it legitimate to ask to what extent democratic societies still have an advantage in dealing with the COVID crisis, as the age structure of their population makes them more vulnerable?

The article builds on the assumption that the fight against the COVID pandemic depends on individual behavior that is out of reach of governmental control (e.g. handwashing with soap and maintaining physical distance), the motivation for complying with the containment measures relying on social capital and social solidarity as core values, both fostered by democracy. We analyze data for 130 countries retrieved from various sources (Our World in Data, the World Bank, Bertelsmann Social Indicators, Freedom House), covering the period between the reporting of the first COVID-19 country and 1 October 2020, using GLS models with AR that allow controlling simultaneously for within and between countries variation of COVID mortality rate.

This paper consists of four parts. The first one presents the theoretical argument regarding the nexus political rule - pandemic. The second part introduces the data, the indicators, and methods, while the third provides the results. The paper concludes with short discussions and recommendations for further research.

Theoretical framework

The connection between political rule and population health is well documented, democracy having a certain advantage as compared to autocracy for several reasons. Democracy goes hand in hand with economic development, leading to growth in education and sanitation and to better healthcare services (Bollyky et al, 2019). Due to political accountability, democratic governments tend to spend more on public health and to provide better healthcare to their citizens (Besley and Kudamatsu, 2006), being particularly effective in controlling cardiovascular diseases, tuberculosis, and traffic injuries (Bollyky et al, 2019). Democratic institutions tend to boost subjective well-being (Inglehart, 2018), leading to better health outcomes and longer life expectancy (Mackebach et al, 2013).

Democracies are better at handling emergencies such as natural disasters or epidemics. To maintain the required level of public support, democratic governments spend an important share of their budget on key public services and infrastructures, which is important in case of emergencies. Freedom of speech and mass media independence from governmental control, prevent the authorities from hiding the truth, keeping the public updated and willing to cooperate with the government (Stromberg, 2007). Defective communication under the autocratic government led to disastrous

consequences during health emergencies in China, in cases such as the Great Famine or the 2003 Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) epidemic (Lin, 2014; Burkle, 2020). Political accountability plays a key role too, motivating democratic governments to react faster when facing natural calamities (Lin, 2014) or health emergencies (Worsnop, 2017). Although people living in democracies prize civil liberties and political freedom, fear and anxiety made them willing to support containment policies, such as quarantine, and the short-term reduction of their rights (Casey, 2015).

In addition, democracy fosters certain social values useful in dealing with a common threat. Democracy goes hand in hand with social capital (Paxton, 2002) leading to tolerance, mutual trust, and confidence in institutions, as well as civic engagement, cooperation, and solidarity (Putnam, 1993; Callero, 2014). By instilling such values, democracy can rely on the full cooperation of its citizens in case of disaster or emergency. While confidence in institutions enhances the cooperation between government and citizens (Sen, 1997), mutual trust, civic engagement, and solidarity foster active involvement with the local community and mutual support among citizens (Story et al, 2018).

Moreover, democratic societies are not equally prepared to face disasters. The literature documents a nexus between political rule and social inequality in shaping the societal answer to emergencies (Patterson and Veenstra, 2016). Social inequality widens the gap in health, general knowledge, and access to public services, health included, which exposes a large share of the public to great risks in case of health emergencies (Strömberg, 2007). Considering the congruence between social solidarity and social structure (Bourgeois and Friedkin, 2001), one can say that social inequality erodes the ability to react in case of emergency due to the lack of cooperation between individuals.

Some autocratic governments proved to be effective in raising life expectancy and improving the health conditions of their citizens, such as China, Cuba, and various communist and fascist regimes in Europe (Navarro, 1992; Mackenbach et al, 2013). In dealing with emergencies and disasters, autocracies may have an advantage because their decisions are not subject to legal or public control, and their populations comply without questioning them (Windholz, 2020).

The COVID outbreak has several particularities that challenge the ability of democratic societies to cope with it. The infection rate is quite high, as compared to SARS and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS), but many of those infected develop only light symptoms, if any (Petersen et al, 2020). However, the infection leads to severe complications and high mortality among adults over 60 years old or among those with pre-existing health conditions (Beam Dowd et al, 2020). The impact of the outbreak is worse in countries with a larger share of the population over 60 (Beam Dowd et al, 2020), exposing democratic societies to greater vulnerability in the face of COVID as they have a higher life expectancy. Moreover, the general public might be less supportive of containment measures, which might include in some cases suspending civil and political rights without a personal benefit.

All governments adopted a wide range of containment measures. While some were intended to prevent the import of cases from abroad, most restrictions aimed at cutting the local chain of transmission. Governments adopted a wide array of measures, including travel restrictions, temporarily closing borders, reducing economic activities, forbidding public events, and closing schools, universities, restaurants, and shopping malls. Governments also implemented mass isolation at home, remote work policies, and reduced human contact. Many of these measures were enforced and controlled by governments, but the most effective measures were those adopted by individuals (Kucharski et al, 2020), residing in, maintaining personal and household hygiene, social distancing, and wearing face masks (WHO 2020). The government could control only the last one, as it occurred in public spaces, while hygiene and social distancing could not be quantified and enforced.

Personal and household hygiene behavior is “private and morally loaded” (Curtis et al, 2011: 318), being highly dependent on the local culture, social norms, the physical and biological barriers (Curtis et al, 2009). Previous research talks about three types of hygiene behavior: habitual, motivational, and planned (Curtis et al, 2009). Habitual behavior is acquired in early childhood and is an automatic controlled behavior being a reflex triggered by special stimuli (like handwashing with soap after using the toilet), while motivational and planned hygiene is consciously assumed, but aiming at different goals. Motivational hygiene is oriented towards short-term goals, being driven by disgust, comfort, affiliation, nurture, status, attraction, and fear of getting sick. Planned hygiene behavior deals with attaining long-term goals related to own and family health, spiritual and religious beliefs, and instilling proper behaviors into the young generation.

Poor hygiene is associated with poverty and low education, but handwashing with soap and household hygiene are not the norm in developed countries (Curtis et al, 2011; Miko et al, 2012). As handwashing with soap is neither a social norm for everyone, nor a habit, extra-motivation is recommended by health authorities. Nurturing and the long-term health of own family seem to be the closest reasons to employ strict hygiene and they require social solidarity and social capital, values fostered by democracy (Sen 1997).

Social distancing, involving minimal contact social and physical contact between people (Oosterhoff et al, 2020), is another key component of the containment policy, linked with personal space. This is the area that individuals maintain around them during interpersonal interactions or an abstract “breathing space” that surrounds each individual (Hall, 1966). Its length varies depending on the individual’s motivation, age, gender, and countries’ temperature (Sorokowska et al, 2017), and on the social setting, the literature distinguishing between social, personal, and intimate distance (Hall, 1966). The length goes from 135 cm for social distance to 31 cm for intimate one, with significant cross-cultural differences being documented (Sorokowska et al, 2017).

The safe interpersonal distance for COVID pandemic is 150-200 cm, higher than the usual average social distance. Therefore, individuals need to adjust this distance when getting in touch with others. The adjustment can occur due to obedience to rules (controlled motivation) or volitionally (autonomous motivation), the second one being strongly connected to prosocial behavior and concerns for the welfare of others (Oosterhoff et al, 2020). As democracy instills prosocial values and behaviors, autonomous motivation adds to rules imposed by the government leading to better control of virus spreading.

Social inequality and polarization play a role too. People keep closer to those alike or belonging to the same group, while groups build spatial boundaries and space groups (Sundstorm and Altman, 1976). Moreover, social exclusion induces the perception of low temperature (Zhong and Lonardelli, 2008) which, in turn, boosts the interpersonal space, as temperature is directly linked to the “breathing space” (Sorokowska et al, 2017). Therefore, one can assume that social polarization keeps people apart, increasing personal space and helping the containment measures. On the other hand, democracy reduces social inequality (Brønnum-Hansen and Baadsgaard, 2012), but we expect that the prosocial culture fostered by democracy compensates for the apparent advantage of polarization that keeps people apart.

Based on this theoretical framework, we state the following hypotheses: (H1) The impact of COVID pandemic is lower in democratic countries. (H2) The impact of COVID pandemic is higher when social inequality is lower. (H3) The higher the level of democratization, the lower the impact of social inequality on the unfolding of the COVID pandemic.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics and sources of data

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Source	Website
CODIV mortality	2,5	113,5	79,4	559,8	Univ. of Oxford	https://ourworldindata.org/mortality-risk-covid
Democratization	2,5	12,4	-2,0	40,0	Freedom House	https://freedomhouse.org/
Social inequality (GINI)	3,8	7,9	24,2	63,0	World Bank	https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SI.POV.GINI
Economic development (GDP)	9,2	1,2	6,6	11,5	Univ. of Oxford	https://ourworldindata.org/mortality-risk-covid
Median age	3,1	9,3	15,1	48,2	Univ. of Oxford	https://ourworldindata.org/mortality-risk-covid
Healthy Life Expectancy Male (60 yo)	14,2	2,5	10,2	19,4	WHO	https://apps.who.int/gho/data/view.main.HALEXv
Healthy Life Expectancy Female (60 yo)	16,2	3,0	10,4	22,9	WHO	https://apps.who.int/gho/data/view.main.HALEXv
Diabetes prevalence	7,1	3,6	1,0	22,0	WHO	https://apps.who.int/gho/data/view.main.HALEXv
Containment& heath stringency index	4,6	1,1	1,2	7,3	WHO	https://apps.who.int/gho/data/view.main.HALEXv
Days since first record	135	38	45	182	Univ. of Oxford	https://ourworldindata.org/mortality-risk-covid

Data and methods

The article employs data retrieved from various sources of aggregate macro-level indicators (see Table 1 for details). We used OLS regression analysis to test the relationship between the impact of COVID and the level of democratization on one hand, and social inequality, on the other hand. The analysis employs listwise deletion of missing values and, after filtering out the cases with missing values, the dataset included 130 cases (the list of countries is available on request).

We use the COVID crude death rate, as reported on 30 June 2020, as the dependent variable to assess the impact of COVID at country-level. We use the 2019 Freedom House Score as a measure of the level of democracy and the GINI Index to measure social inequality.

We controlled for several variables having documented impact on COVID death rate, such as the Government Stringency Index (average value of Containment and Health components across countries as of 30 June 2020) that taps the impact of containment measures and the governmental support to health services (Hale et al, 2020), the level of economic development, captured by the natural logarithm of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita, wealthy countries being better able to deal with the virus as they have more effective healthcare systems (Besley and Kudamatsu, 2006), while the general level of education and of hygiene behavior is higher among their public (Curtis et al, 2011).

The median age stands for the age structure of the population, countries with older population having a higher likelihood of recording numerous casualties (Beam Dowd et al, 2020). We tap the preexisting morbidities with the help of the healthy life expectancy at the age of 60 by gender, as men have a higher likelihood of developing severe conditions (Beam Dowd et al, 2020). As diabetes is one of the most relevant comorbidities and data for a large number of countries are available, we included it in the model. The number of days since the first report on COVID pandemic in a country stands for the length of health emergency, which can influence the mortality rate, the longer the length the higher mortality recorded (Baud et al, 2020). Descriptive statistics for the dependent and independent variables are provided in Table 1.

Data analysis

The data shown in Figure 1 indicates a negative association between the democracy index and COVID mortality: the higher the level of democratization, the lower the COVID mortality rate. In spite of the death toll paid by societies having a large share of old adults, as many democracies are, they still preserve their net advantage in fighting against the pandemic. Figure 2 displays the connection between COVID mortality and social inequality, and the results are not very conclusive, the pattern of association being rather elusive.

We run three OLS regression models, with the results being shown in Table 2. The first one includes only the main independent variables, level of democratization and social inequality, as well as the interaction between them, and it accounts for 33% of the cross-national variation in COVID mortality. The next two models employ control variables, the second one controlling for the regular associates of mortality in cross-national design, while the third adds variables regarding the specifics of COVID pandemic. The variables in model 2 taken together explain 66% of the variation in COVID mortality, while by adding the variables directly linked with the current pandemic (Stringency index, time since the first reporting, prevalence of diabetes) the R^2 goes up to 67%. Thus, the cross-countries variation in COVID mortality is shared almost equally between political rule and social structure, on one side, and wealth in a country together with population structure and its general health, on the other side.

Figure 1. COVID mortality by level of democracy in 130 countries

Figure 2. COVID mortality by level of social inequality in 130 countries

Table 2. Standardized and unstandardized regression coefficients. Dependent variable: COVID death rates

	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	Coef.	Beta	SE	Coef.	Beta	SE	Coef.	Beta	SE
Democratization	-17,779	-1,94	3,769	-9,635	-1,051	3,00	-8,007	-0,873	3,07
Social inequality	-12,258	-0,85	2,977	-7,364	-0,512	2,33	-6,992	-0,481	2,32
Democratization * Social inequality	0,365	1,58	0,102	0,196	0,847	0,81	0,161	0,699	0,08
Economic development				-14,332	-0,146	10,81	-21,252	-0,217	11,85
Median age				5,165	0,424	1,74	4,745	0,390	1,76
Healthy Life Expectancy Male (60 y.o)				-37,707	-0,820	8,51	-40,480	-0,881	8,90
Healthy Life Expectancy Female (60 y.o)				3,638	0,950	9,26	6,679	0,175	9,62
Diabetes prevalence							3,613	0,114	1,92
Containment& heath stringency index							7,212	0,072	5,36
Days since first record							0,033	0,011	0,21
Constant	818,126		111,158	1038,821		112,13	1016,48		
R ²	0,33			0,65			0,67		

The results of the OLS regression support our first hypothesis, pointing out to the negative relation between democratization and COVID mortality. Across all models, the level of democratization has a strong impact on COVID mortality, and after controlling for all independent variables, it still has the second largest effect on the target variable. The second hypothesis is supported by the data, too: countries with higher levels of social inequality are reporting lower mortality rates, as shown in all three models. However, the effect on COVID mortality is as large as half of the effect of democratization. Although we expected democracy to wipe out the impact of social inequality, the results indicate that the COVID death toll is higher in social settings combining social inequality and democratization, the effect of the interaction on the target variable being the third largest in the third model.

Most of the control variables have the expected impact on the dependent variable. Economic development goes hand in hand with low COVID mortality, while population ageing and the large prevalence of diabetes lead to a high death toll. One should notice how the health conditions of old adults impact differently on COVID mortality depending on sex. While low healthy life expectancy at the age of 60 among men boosts the death toll, the relation is the opposite in the case of women. In countries where old men are in bad health conditions, COVID mortality is high, because the number of those having co-morbidities is high. When women are in good health until late in their lives, they live longer and their share in the old population is high. The variables directly linked to the management of healthy emergency, containment measures, and time since the first report, have only a marginal impact on the cross-country differences in death toll. This is most likely an artifact of the cross-sectional research design, which does not look at the overtime change of the death rate combined with the containment measures, but rather at the cross-national variability of these measures and their impact on COVID mortality.

Conclusions

This paper looks at the interplay between political rule and social structure and COVID mortality. The purpose is to investigate whether democracy still preserves its advantage in fighting against the health emergency despite the high fatality rate among old adults. The results indicate that although increasing life expectancy is one of the main mechanisms for reducing mortality in democratic societies, even when increased life expectancy raises vulnerability, democratic governments do better in containing the pandemic. We assume that the core values instilled by democracy can be employed to explain this result, however further research is needed to provide empirical support to this interpretation.

The second hypothesis is also supported by the data, social inequality being associated with reduced COVID mortality. Higher inequality keeps people apart, the impact of social distancing compensating for the lower level of solidarity. However, further research is needed to shed light on how much personal distance matters for the containment measures and to what extent social capital and solidarity prevent the spreading of the infection, especially towards those vulnerable.

The data do not provide support for the third hypothesis. Social inequality leads to different health outcomes across social strata, the better off living longer and in good health, while the general life expectancy and the healthy life expectancy are lower among those at the bottom end of the social structure (Wilkinson, 1992; Brønnum-Hansen and Baadsgaard, 2016). The combination of democracy and social inequality may lead to double risk in facing the COVID pandemic: a larger share of old adults among the better off and a higher share of mature adults in rather poor health conditions. While the first group is vulnerable to COVID due to age, the second one faces the risks brought by co-morbidities. In addition, social inequality has a negative impact on solidarity and cohesion (Van de Werfhorst and

Salverda, 2012), making people less willing to adapt their behavior (maintaining hygiene and social distancing). Further research is needed to understand how the nexus democracy–social inequality shapes the effect of the COVID pandemic.

We can conclude that political rule matters for the management of a pandemic, as well as social inequality. However, this is only the first scratch, detailed analyses are required to prove the precise contribution of social capital and social solidarity to the implementation of containment measures.

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